

ANTECEDENTS OF GENDER STEREOTYPING AMONG SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

○ JOJAMES ARNALDO G. GADDI ○

○ MELISSA P. MACABODBOD ○

○ AJ MARIELLE P. PONGCOL ○

○ ANDREI JOHN MATTHEW C. LIPIO ○

○ STEPHANIE PAULA MENDOZA ○

St. Paul University Surigao
mr.jojamesgaddi@gmail.com

Received: 31 August 2024 / Accepted: 3 October 2024/ Published: 30 October 2024
© Philippine Association for Teachers & Educators (PAFTE), Inc. 2024

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the antecedents of gender stereotyping among senior high school students and the factors that sustain these stereotypes in a private school in Surigao City, Philippines. To assess the antecedents, the study examined the following variables: individual factors, cognitive factors, family factors, and socio-cultural factors. Stratified random sampling was employed to select senior high school students enrolled in the academic year 2023–2024 as participants. The results revealed that the perspectives of senior high school students on gender are occasionally influenced by individual, cognitive, family, and socio-cultural factors. A significant difference was observed across all factors when grouped according to their academic strand. Among these, family emerged as the most influential factor, highlighting its critical role in perpetuating

gender stereotypes, particularly in relation to household responsibilities and gendered roles within the family unit. The study recommends that students enhance their awareness of behaviors that may reinforce stereotypes and reflect on the factors shaping their gender perceptions and actions. This self-awareness is essential in fostering more equitable attitudes and behaviors.

Keywords: antecedents, gender stereotyping, gendered roles, senior high school students

INTRODUCTION

Gender stereotyping has long posed a significant obstacle to achieving true gender equality and continues to perpetuate gender discrimination. This pervasive and multifaceted issue impacts various aspects of individual and societal life, including education, career opportunities, and personal relationships. Gender stereotypes often lead to discrimination, prejudice, and bias against individuals who deviate from traditional gender roles and expectations. Individual, family, cognitive, and socio-cultural factors collectively shape and sustain stereotypical thinking, thereby reinforcing gender stereotypes (Tabassum & Nayak, 2021).

In a study by Bian et al. (2017), the effects of gender stereotyping on children's development were explored, revealing that common stereotypes associate high-level intellectual abilities, such as brilliance and genius, more frequently with men than women. These stereotypes, once internalized, influence children's interests and significantly narrow the range of careers they consider pursuing. According to the researchers, cultural messages about presumed cognitive abilities of males and females drive these perceptions.

In the Philippines, the country ranked 17th among 156 nations in closing gender inequality, as reported by the World Economic Forum's *Global Gender Gap Report 2021*. While the Philippines has closed

78.4% of its overall gender gap, making it the top-performing country in Asia, persistent gender stereotypes in academic and workplace settings undermine this progress. Research by The Women and Gender Institute (UNESCO, n.d.) highlights the prevalence of workplace discrimination based on sexual orientation and gender identity. This issue is shaped by a complex interplay of social, cultural, and historical factors. Traditional Filipino values emphasize distinct gender roles, where men are seen as providers and leaders, while women are associated with nurturing and supportive roles, restricting individuals' career choices and aspirations. Culturally, the concept of "bayanihan" reinforces women's caregiving roles while underrepresenting them in leadership positions. Media portrayals frequently depict women as homemakers, further perpetuating these stereotypes. Historically, the Philippines' colonial past imposed patriarchal norms that marginalized women, limiting their access to education and public life. Despite significant progress, remnants of these inequities persist today.

At St. Paul University Surigao (SPU Surigao), anecdotal evidence suggests that gender stereotyping remains prevalent, affecting both students and faculty members. Traditional expectations, such as "boys should be loud and boisterous" and "girls should be prim and proper," continue to shape perceptions and interactions within the university. These stereotypes limit students' self-expression and hinder their aspirations, particularly in pursuing careers traditionally associated with the opposite gender, such as becoming uniformed personnel. However, a significant gap in research exists regarding the antecedents of gender stereotyping among senior high school students at SPU Surigao. Understanding these antecedents is essential to addressing the root causes of gender stereotyping in the school environment.

To address this research gap, this study aims to investigate the antecedents of gender stereotyping at SPU Surigao, focusing on individual, socio-cultural, familial, and cognitive factors. By identifying the causes of gender stereotyping, the study seeks to foster a more inclusive and equitable environment within the university and provide

insights that could serve as a model for other institutions facing similar challenges.

Gender Stereotyping

Gender stereotypes are deeply rooted in local culture and traditions. Children learn gendered behaviors and expectations from various sources, including family, peers, media, schools, and religious institutions. These stereotypes can negatively affect all genders, as young people are frequently exposed to societal messages about how boys and girls should look, behave, and play. These socially accepted and often unconscious ideas begin to take shape as early as infancy (UNESCO, n.d.).

The issue has become increasingly prevalent and pressing in contemporary society, reflecting the expectations of specific social groups (Ellemers, 2018). Gender stereotypes also significantly influence academic self-concept through social relationships and interactions (Ertl et al., 2017; Rost et al., 2005). Parents and teachers, often unconsciously, project their own gender stereotypes onto children by assessing and appraising academic abilities in ways that align with these biases. For instance, when girls receive more encouragement for excelling in traditionally female-dominated subjects such as English or history, they are more likely to internalize these stereotypes into their academic self-concept (Ertl et al., 2017).

Individual Factors

Physical attributes serve as a primary component in both the formation and perpetuation of gender stereotypes. These stereotypes often stem from societal expectations regarding how individuals should look based on their gender, contributing significantly to the way people are perceived and treated in various social contexts. According to Dökmen (2012), as cited by Gul Unlu (2021), one of the most significant aspects of gender stereotyping lies in the assessment of an individual's physical appearance. This is crucial because a person's physical appearance is often the initial and most readily observable aspect through which stereotypes are

projected onto others. As such, individuals are frequently judged and categorized based on their physical attributes, leading to preconceived notions about their abilities, traits, and behaviors. This expectation to conform to societal norms based on appearance can exert considerable pressure on individuals to align with stereotypical expectations, influencing how they present themselves and interact with others (Gaddi, 2024).

In addition to evaluating physical appearance, perpetuating gender stereotyping can also occur through making jokes about one's gender. These jests and humorous remarks often reinforce existing stereotypes and prejudices, contributing to the normalization of discriminatory attitudes and behaviors. These preconceived notions then form the basis for how individuals are treated, potentially perpetuating stereotypes and prejudices (Law et al., 2021). Such discussions or jokes may reinforce existing stereotypes and prejudices, especially when they promote negative stereotypes about specific groups. This behavior can fuel discrimination, hinder genuine connections, and contribute to a negative social atmosphere, thereby impacting individuals' self-esteem and opportunities for personal development. Zawisza et al. (2018) further argues that stereotypes create a vicious cycle wherein stigmatized individuals experience anxiety, depleting their cognitive resources, leading to underperformance, reinforcing negative stereotypes, and perpetuating fear.

Cognitive Factors

One's cognition significantly influences gender stereotyping, shaping perceptions, attitudes, and behaviors toward individuals based on their gender. Cognitive processes such as categorization, schema activation, and information processing play crucial roles in the formation and reinforcement of gender stereotypes. Individuals tend to categorize others into gender groups based on observable characteristics, which subsequently activate corresponding gender schemas, mental frameworks containing expectations and beliefs about how individuals of a particular

gender should behave. These schemas guide the interpretation of information, reinforcing gender stereotypes through selective attention, memory recall, and judgment processes. Additionally, cognitive biases such as confirmation bias and stereotype threat further sustain gender stereotyping by reinforcing existing beliefs and influencing performance in gender-stereotyped domains.

According to the Fawcett Society (2023), engaging in gender stereotyping limits individuals by constraining them within narrow and often unrealistic societal expectations based on their gender. By perpetuating stereotypes and reinforcing traditional gender roles, individuals are restricted in expressing their identity, aspirations, and capabilities. This limitation hinders personal growth and fulfillment while perpetuating inequality and discrimination within society, obstructing progress toward a more inclusive and equitable world (Languing et al., 2023; Eliot et al., 2024; Gaddi, 2024).

Despite these evident negative effects, people often unconsciously perpetuate gender stereotypes. This phenomenon can be explained by Lewicki's (1986) Theory of Non-conscious Detection of Co-variation, which posits that once individuals form a non-conscious association between two events, they tend to continue the same behavior even after the association loses relevance. The self-perpetuating nature of stereotype formation is further reinforced through continued behavior and social interactions, maintaining and amplifying these stereotypes over time.

Family Factors

Family dynamics play a significant role in perpetuating gender stereotyping through various mechanisms. As Kane (1996), cited by Lumen Learning (2023), highlights, children learn distinct gender expectations from an early age, primarily through socialization within the family unit. Parents often reinforce traditional gender roles and behaviors through their actions, attitudes, and expectations toward their children. For instance, boys may be encouraged to participate in activities deemed masculine, such as sports or outdoor play, while girls are often steered

toward domestic tasks or nurturing behaviors. This process ingrains gender stereotypes in children early on, shaping their understanding of appropriate behavior based on their gender. Additionally, family members may unintentionally transmit gender biases through daily interactions, such as praising behaviors in one gender while discouraging them in another (Cabrigas et al., 2024).

Tabassum and Nayak (2021) further emphasize that within the family, children are exposed to social interactions, experiences, and role models that significantly influence their psychological and emotional growth. Parents play a central role in shaping their child's personality through their behavior, attitudes, and interactions. Children often model their own behaviors and beliefs after those of their parents, internalizing parental values, expectations, and norms as they navigate their social environments. Similarly, Ebert et al. (2024) argue that the family serves as the primary agent of socialization, being the first environment where children encounter societal norms, values, and behaviors. These early experiences within the family context provide the foundation for children's social and cognitive development, influencing their attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors as they engage with the broader social world.

Socio-cultural Factors

The socio-cultural environment plays a significant role in perpetuating gender stereotyping by shaping societal norms, values, and expectations regarding gender roles and behaviors. Cultural beliefs and traditions often reinforce traditional gender norms, prescribing specific roles and behaviors for men and women (Platil et al., 2024; Gaddi, 2024). For instance, media representations, advertisements, and popular culture frequently depict stereotypical portrayals of gender, reinforcing societal perceptions of masculinity and femininity. Sociology establishes that society perpetuates gender roles through gender socialization, occurring via four major agents of socialization: family, schools, peer groups, and mass media. Each agent reinforces gender roles by maintaining normative expectations for gender-specific behavior (Lumen Learning, 2023; Diaz et al., 2024).

One of the most pervasive stereotypes in society pertains to emotions, with societal expectations often dictating how individuals express and perceive emotional experiences. Shafi (2021) argues that men and women experience emotions at similar levels, challenging the stereotype that men are less emotional than women. However, societal norms discourage men from openly expressing vulnerability or sadness, perpetuating the misconception that men do not experience these emotions. This pressure compels many men to suppress their emotions to conform to societal expectations, fearing ridicule or perceived weakness. Such emotional suppression can have detrimental effects on men's mental health, contributing to conditions like depression, anxiety, and emotional distress.

Despite efforts at reform and adaptation, gender stereotypes surrounding emotions persist. Islam and Asadullah (2018) emphasize that entrenched attitudes continue to be reinforced by societal structures and media representations. The pervasive influence of these societal norms and portrayals perpetuates traditional gender roles, making it difficult to dismantle deeply ingrained stereotypes. While progress toward greater gender equality has been made, these persistent stereotypes underscore the need for continued awareness, education, and advocacy to challenge harmful societal perceptions of gender and emotions. Promoting inclusivity and encouraging individuals of all genders to express their emotions openly and authentically are critical for fostering healthier and more supportive communities (Gaddi et al., 2024; Dacoylo et al., 2024).

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the antecedents of gender stereotyping among senior high school students. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the participants in terms of:
 - 1.1. Gender;
 - 1.2. Strand; and
 - 1.3. Religion?

2. What are the antecedents of gender stereotyping among senior high school students in terms of:
 - 2.1. Individual factors;
 - 2.2. Cognitive factors;
 - 2.3. Family factors; and
 - 2.4. Socio-cultural factors?
3. Is there a significant difference in the antecedents of gender stereotyping among senior high school students when grouped according to their profile?

METHODS

The descriptive research design was utilized in this study, alongside the survey method. This design was suitable for determining the antecedents of gender stereotyping among Senior High School students at St. Paul University Surigao. Descriptive research, as McCombes (2019) explains, aims to accurately and systematically describe a population, situation, or phenomenon. While it can answer questions such as what, where, when, and how, it does not address why. A descriptive research design can incorporate a variety of research methods to investigate one or more variables.

The participants of this study were 272 senior high school students from St. Paul University Surigao during the school year 2023–2024. They were selected using stratified random sampling, with the sample size determined through Slovin's formula. This sampling technique ensured that all participants represented the population adequately. The study also ensured balanced representation of gender and academic strands, including STEM, HUMSS, ABM, and TVL. This balanced distribution enhanced the reliability and validity of the findings, providing a comprehensive understanding of gender stereotypes among the student body.

A researcher-made questionnaire was developed and subjected

to comprehensive validation and reliability testing. A panel of experts in gender studies, education, and research methodology reviewed the questionnaire for content validity, assessing its clarity, relevance, and comprehensiveness in relation to the study's objectives. The computed Content Validity Index (CVI) for the questionnaire was 0.85, surpassing the acceptable threshold of 0.80. Items falling below this threshold were revised or removed to ensure validity.

Following validation, the questionnaire underwent pilot testing with 30 students from a nearby school to assess its reliability and address any potential issues. The pilot test results were used to calculate Cronbach's alpha, which measured internal consistency. The overall Cronbach's alpha was 0.82, exceeding the accepted threshold of 0.70, indicating good reliability for measuring the intended variables.

The final questionnaire was divided into two parts. Part I collected demographic information about the participants, including gender, strand, and religion. Part II focused on identifying the antecedents of gender stereotyping, operationally defined as follows:

Individual Factors: These refer to physical differences, such as race and gender, and external threats causing stereotypes. For example, participants were asked whether they had judged characteristics as exclusively masculine or feminine.

Cognitive Factors: These include mental processes, such as assumptions and judgments, that lead to gender stereotyping. Items addressed differential treatment based on gender, pressure to conform to gender roles, and preconceived notions about abilities.

Family Factors: These involve family influences, such as gender-specific responsibilities and behaviors instilled by family members. Items examined beliefs about household chores, career suitability, and discouragement of gender-nonconforming interests.

Socio-Cultural Factors: These include societal norms and cultural practices that perpetuate stereotypes. Items prompted reflection on norms for acceptable gender behavior, stereotype-reinforcing language, and

emotional suppression based on gender.

A formal letter was sent to the Principal of the Basic Education Department at St. Paul University Surigao to seek permission to administer the questionnaire. Upon approval, a second letter was sent to the participants, explaining the study's purpose and requesting their consent. Participants were informed of their rights, including the ability to ask questions and withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. Data collection spanned two weeks to allow participants sufficient time to complete the questionnaire.

During data collection, logistical challenges included coordinating schedules with students and addressing initial hesitancy from participants. Concerns about how responses would be used were mitigated by emphasizing the confidentiality and voluntary nature of the study. Ethical measures included:

Informed Consent: The principal and participants provided informed consent after being fully briefed on the study's objectives, their roles, and their rights, including the right to withdraw.

Confidentiality: Personal information, including gender and academic data, was anonymized to protect participants' privacy.

Professionalism and Objectivity: Researchers maintained professionalism to avoid bias or influencing responses, ensuring the integrity of the collected data.

After data collection, responses were tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted using the following statistical tools:

Frequency Count and Percentage Distribution: These tools described participants' demographic profiles, including gender, strand, and religion.

Mean and Standard Deviation: These statistical measures analyzed the antecedents of gender stereotyping among the students.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA): This test determined significant differences in the antecedents of gender stereotyping based on participants' demographic profiles.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Participants Demographic Profile

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the participants in terms profiles regarding sex, strand, and religion.

Table 1. *Demographic Profile of the Participants*

Profile	f (271)	%
Sex		
Male	114	42
Female	157	58
Strand		
ABM	42	16
ADT/TVL	21	8
HUMSS	66	24
STEM	142	52
Religion		
INC	15	6
Roman Catholic	219	81
Islam	3	1
Others	34	13

Out of 271 senior high school students, in terms of sex, most of the participants are females with 157 (58%) while 114 (42%) are males. As for strand, there are more STEM students who participated with 142 responses (52%), followed by HUMSS with 66 responses (24%), ABM with 42 participants (16%), and ADT/TVL with 21 participants (8%). As to the religious affiliations of the participants, majority of them are Roman Catholics with 219 (81%), 34 participants (13%) answered others, while 15 students (6%) are INC, and about 3 participants (1%) answered that they are Muslims. The data reveals a strong female presence, significant interest in STEM education, and a predominantly Catholic

population among the participants. These profile variables reflect both the local demographic trends and educational preferences, highlighting the possible cultural and academic inclinations of the students in this region. Studies have shown that female participation in education is notably high in the Philippines, with females consistently outperforming and outnumbering males in higher education enrollment (Orbeta, 2019). Additionally, the growing focus on STEM education aligns with national initiatives aimed at addressing the demand for science and technology professionals, as outlined by the Department of Education’s push for STEM programs (DepEd, 2019). The dominance of Roman Catholicism among participants is consistent with the Philippines’ religious makeup, where over 80% of the population identifies as Catholic, deeply influencing cultural values and practices in educational settings (Pew Research Center, 2019). These findings highlight the intersection of gender, academic preferences, and religious affiliation in shaping the cultural and academic inclinations of students in this region.

Antecedents of Gender Stereotyping among Senior High School

Table 2 illustrates the antecedents of gender stereotyping among Senior High School students in terms of Individual, Cognitive, Family, and Socio-cultural Factors.

Table 2. *Antecedents of Gender Stereotyping among Senior High School students in terms of Individual, Cognitive, Family, and Socio-cultural Factors*

Indicators	M	SD	CI (95%)	ES (Cohen’s d)	VI	QD
Individual Factors						
1. I have used physical appearance as a basis for determining someone’s value or worth.	2.58	1.16	(2.44, 2.72)	0.50	A	O

2. I have used language or comments that reinforce traditional gender stereotypes related to physical appearance.	2.40	1.03	(2.27, 2.53)	0.44	D	S
3. I have made assumptions about certain physical features that are exclusively masculine or feminine.	2.49	1.03	(2.36, 2.62)	0.49	D	S
4. I have excluded or marginalized individuals because their physical appearance did not align with societal gender norms.	2.32	1.11	(2.19, 2.45)	0.44	D	S
5. I have participated in discussions or jokes about how an individual acts or look.	2.31	1.16	(2.17, 2.45)	0.43	D	S

Average	2.42	1.10	(2.32, 2.52)	0.46	D	S
---------	------	------	--------------	------	---	---

Cognitive Factors

1. I have made assumptions about people's interests or preferences in various areas, such as career choices or hobbies, based solely on their gender.	2.65	1.07	(2.32, 2.58)	0.61	A	O
2. I have treated individuals differently because of their gender.	2.33	1.03	(2.25, 2.51)	0.32	D	S
3. I have pressured or encouraged individuals to conform to specific roles and standards based on their gender.	2.36	1.08	(2.23, 2.49)	0.33	D	S
4. I have attributed certain behaviors or personality traits to individuals based on their gender.	2.42	1.02	(2.19, 2.45)	0.41	D	S
5. I have made judgments about someone's capabilities or competence based on preconceived notions about their gender.	2.30	1.13	(2.41, 2.67)	0.27	D	S

Average	2.41	1.07	(2.30, 2.52)	0.38	D	S
Family Factors						
1. I have been taught by my family that certain household chores or responsibilities are solely designated for a specific gender.	2.85	1.13	(2.72, 2.98)	0.62	A	O
2. I have been raised with the belief that certain career paths or professional aspirations are more suitable for one gender over another.	2.59	1.06	(2.46, 2.72)	0.53	A	O
3. I have witnessed or experienced my family discouraging or disapproving of activities or interests that are considered 'unfit' for my gender.	2.59	1.09	(2.46, 2.72)	0.53	A	O
4. I have been taught gender-specific behaviors or mannerisms that align with societal expectations.	2.71	1.08	(2.26, 2.52)	0.44	A	O
5. I have been raised with the belief that my personal relationships or friendships should follow gender-specific norms.	2.58	1.14	(2.45, 2.71)	0.53	A	O
Average	2.66	1.10	(2.49, 2.71)	0.53	A	O
Socio-cultural Factors						
1. I have conformed to societal norms that dictate appropriate behavior, appearance, or interests based on my gender.	2.56	1.03	(2.30, 2.56)	0.44	A	O
2. I have used language or expressions that reinforce gender stereotypes and perpetuate unequal power dynamics.	2.47	1.09	(2.36, 2.62)	0.47	D	S

3.	I have dismissed or downplayed instances of gender-based discrimination or harassment by attributing them to ‘normal’ or acceptable behavior.	2.48	1.07	(2.40, 2.66)	0.49	D	S
4.	I have accepted and perpetuated double standards regarding sexual behavior or promiscuity based on societal expectations of gender.	2.58	1.06	(2.45, 2.71)	0.53	A	O
5.	I have reinforced the notion that emotional expression or vulnerability is discouraged or seen as weak based on societal expectations tied to gender.	2.39	1.10	(2.53, 2.79)	0.56	D	S
Average		2.50	1.07	(2.43, 2.65)	0.50	D	S
Overall Average		2.50	1.08	(2.40, 2.60)	0.48	D	S

Scale	Interval	Verbal Interpretation	Code	Qualitative Description	Code
4	3.25-4.00	<i>Strongly Agree</i>	SA	<i>Always</i>	A
3	2.50-3.24	<i>Agree</i>	A	<i>Often</i>	O
2	1.75-2.49	<i>Disagree</i>	D	<i>Sometimes</i>	S
1	1.00-1.74	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	SD	<i>Never</i>	N

Out of the five indicators for the variable Individual Factors, Indicator 1, “I have used physical appearance as a basis for determining someone’s value or worth,” obtained the highest mean score ($M = 2.58$, $SD = 1.16$, $95\% \text{ CI } [2.44, 2.72]$), with a moderate effect size (Cohen’s $d = 0.50$), verbally interpreted as Agree and qualitatively described as Often. This suggests that students frequently rely on superficial attributes, particularly physical appearance, to evaluate others, reflecting

a significant tendency toward surface-level judgment. The notable effect size indicates practical significance, reinforcing the role of physical appearance in shaping perceptions. This bias may lead to neglecting intrinsic qualities such as talents, character, or personality. As Dökmen (2012), cited by Gul Unlu (2021), emphasizes, physical appearance is one of the most accessible components of gender stereotyping, and this reliance perpetuates social biases. The pressure to conform to societal beauty standards consequently shapes how individuals present themselves and how they are perceived.

In contrast, Indicator 5, “I have participated in discussions or jokes about how an individual acts or looks,” received the lowest mean score ($M = 2.31$, $SD = 1.16$, 95% CI [2.17, 2.45], Cohen’s $d = 0.43$), verbally interpreted as Disagree and qualitatively described as Sometimes. Although students occasionally engage in such behavior, the moderate effect size indicates its potential consequences. Even casual jokes or discussions may subtly reinforce stereotypes and normalize prejudicial attitudes. According to Ford et al. (2024), humor based on appearance or behavior can solidify harmful stereotypes, especially when repeated in social settings, even if unintentional.

Overall, the average for Individual Factors was $M = 2.42$ ($SD = 1.10$, 95% CI [2.32, 2.52], Cohen’s $d = 0.46$), verbally interpreted as Disagree and qualitatively described as Sometimes. This indicates that while students do not consistently stereotype others based on appearance, such behaviors persist. The moderate effect size suggests that these stereotypes, though not predominant, have a tangible impact on social dynamics. Zawisza (2018) notes that stereotypes create a feedback loop, where judgment based on appearance causes heightened anxiety, leading to underperformance and further entrenching negative perceptions.

For Cognitive Factors, Indicator 1, “I have made assumptions about people’s interests or preferences in various areas, such as career choices or hobbies, based solely on their gender,” recorded the highest mean score ($M = 2.65$, $SD = 1.07$, 95% CI [2.32, 2.58], Cohen’s $d = 0.61$), verbally interpreted as Agree and qualitatively described as Often.

The moderate effect size highlights the practical significance of gender-based assumptions, suggesting that gender continues to shape students' perceptions of interests and career paths. As the Fawcett Society (2023) asserts, such assumptions limit young people's options, reinforce societal gender norms, and contribute to gender disparities in education and the workforce.

Conversely, Indicator 5, "I have made judgments about someone's capabilities or competence based on preconceived notions about their gender," had the lowest mean score ($M = 2.30$, $SD = 1.13$, 95% CI [2.41, 2.67], Cohen's $d = 0.27$), verbally interpreted as Disagree and qualitatively described as Sometimes. Although these judgments are less frequent, they remain significant. This finding aligns with the Philippines' 16th-place ranking in the 2023 Global Gender Gap Index by the World Economic Forum, reflecting progress toward more equitable treatment in education and the workplace.

The overall average for Cognitive Factors was $M = 2.41$ ($SD = 1.07$, 95% CI [2.30, 2.52], Cohen's $d = 0.38$), verbally interpreted as Disagree and qualitatively described as Sometimes. While students occasionally rely on gender stereotypes, the behavior is not dominant. The moderate effect size suggests that stereotypes persist due to unconscious cognitive biases, as explained by Lewicki's (1986) Theory of Non-conscious Detection of Co-variation. This theory posits that individuals may continue applying disproven stereotypes unconsciously.

For Family Factors, Indicator 1, "I have been taught by my family that certain household chores or responsibilities are solely designated for a specific gender," had the highest mean score ($M = 2.85$, $SD = 1.13$, 95% CI [2.72, 2.98], Cohen's $d = 0.62$), verbally interpreted as Agree and qualitatively described as Often. This indicates a moderate to large effect size, highlighting the family's role in reinforcing gender roles. Kane (1996), cited by Lumen Learning (2023), notes that the internalization of gender roles begins at a young age through family teachings.

Indicator 5, “I have been raised with the belief that my personal relationships or friendships should follow gender-specific norms,” recorded the lowest mean score ($M = 2.58$, $SD = 1.14$, 95% CI [2.45, 2.71], Cohen’s $d = 0.53$), verbally interpreted as Agree and qualitatively described as Often. The moderate effect size suggests these beliefs still influence interpersonal dynamics. Tabassum and Nayak (2021) emphasize that families significantly shape children’s views on gender roles.

The overall mean for Family Factors was $M = 2.66$ ($SD = 1.10$, 95% CI [2.49, 2.71], Cohen’s $d = 0.53$), verbally interpreted as Agree and qualitatively described as Often. The findings reinforce the family’s substantial influence on students’ gender-related beliefs, as families are primary agents of socialization (Ebert et al., 2024).

For Socio-cultural Factors, Indicator 4, “I have accepted and perpetuated double standards regarding sexual behavior or promiscuity based on societal expectations of gender,” recorded the highest mean score ($M = 2.58$, $SD = 1.06$, 95% CI [2.45, 2.71], Cohen’s $d = 0.53$), verbally interpreted as Agree and qualitatively described as Often. This reflects societal norms that apply different standards to men and women, reinforcing unequal treatment.

Indicator 5, “I have reinforced the notion that emotional expression or vulnerability is discouraged or seen as weak based on societal expectations tied to gender,” had the lowest mean score ($M = 2.39$, $SD = 1.10$, 95% CI [2.53, 2.79], Cohen’s $d = 0.56$), verbally interpreted as Disagree and qualitatively described as Sometimes. This suggests a growing awareness of emotional well-being, challenging traditional norms.

The overall mean for Socio-cultural Factors was $M = 2.50$ ($SD = 1.07$, 95% CI [2.43, 2.65], Cohen’s $d = 0.50$), verbally interpreted as Disagree and qualitatively described as Sometimes. This suggests occasional influence of socio-cultural factors on students’ gender perspectives. Islam and Asadullah (2018) highlight the media’s role in perpetuating stereotypes within Filipino society.

To sum, among the variables, Family Factors had the highest mean ($M = 2.66$, $SD = 1.10$), indicating the strongest influence on students' gender beliefs, while Cognitive Factors had the lowest mean ($M = 2.41$, $SD = 1.07$), suggesting growing awareness of gender stereotypes' harmful effects. The overall mean was $M = 2.50$ ($SD = 1.08$, 95% CI [2.40, 2.60], Cohen's $d = 0.48$), verbally interpreted as Disagree and qualitatively described as Sometimes. While gender stereotypes remain prevalent, there is a gradual shift toward more equitable attitudes, consistent with the Philippines' progress in gender equality as indicated by the 2023 Global Gender Gap Index.

Significant Difference on the Antecedents of Gender Stereotype among Senior High School

Table 3 presents significant differences in the antecedents of gender stereotyping among senior high school students in terms of individual factors, cognitive factors, family factors, and socio-cultural factors when grouped according to their profile, such as sex, strand, and religion.

Table 3. *Significant Difference on the Antecedents of Gender Stereotyping among Senior High School Students when grouped according to their profile variables*

Profile	Factors	F	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Sex	Individual Factors	3.231	0.073	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
	Cognitive Factors	2.303	0.130	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
	Family Factors	0.617	0.433	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
	Socio-cultural Factors	0.742	0.390	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Strand	Individual Factors	4.465	0.004	Reject Ho	Significant
	Cognitive Factors	6.041	0.001	Reject Ho	Significant
	Family Factors	3.857	0.010	Reject Ho	Significant
	Socio-cultural Factors	4.246	0.006	Reject Ho	Significant

	Individual Factors	3.884	0.010	Reject Ho	Significant
Religion	Cognitive Factors	1.780	0.151	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
	Family Factors	0.880	0.452	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
	Socio-cultural Factors	1.671	0.174	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant

The findings reveal no significant differences in the antecedents of gender stereotyping among senior high school students in terms of Individual Factors ($p = 0.073$), Cognitive Factors ($p = 0.130$), Family Factors ($p = 0.433$), and Socio-cultural Factors ($p = 0.390$) concerning their sex. Since the respective p -values are higher than the expected level of significance (0.05), the hypothesis is not rejected. This indicates that the antecedents of gender stereotyping among senior high school students do not significantly differ based on their sex. This implies that regardless of whether students are male or female, they are similarly influenced by individual, cognitive, family, and socio-cultural factors in relation to gender stereotyping. One potential explanation for these non-significant differences could be cultural similarities and shared socialization patterns within the sample, fostering common beliefs and attitudes about gender. Limited exposure to non-traditional gender roles within their environment may also contribute to these uniform perspectives. This interpretation aligns with Rudman and Goodwin (2004), as cited by Bosak et al. (2017), who noted that both men and women can hold and propagate gender stereotypes, though the specifics and focus of these stereotypes may vary.

In terms of strand, there is a significant difference in the antecedents of gender stereotyping among senior high school students for Individual Factors ($p = 0.004$), Cognitive Factors ($p = 0.001$), Family Factors ($p = 0.010$), and Socio-cultural Factors ($p = 0.006$). Since the respective p -values are lower than the expected level of significance (0.05), the hypothesis is rejected. This suggests that the academic strand influences students' perceptions of gender stereotypes, potentially shaped by curriculum content, peer influence, teacher expectations, and access to opportunities. For instance, certain strands may inadvertently reinforce stereotypes by emphasizing subjects traditionally associated

with specific genders or by promoting unequal expectations for male and female students. Peer groups within different strands may also reinforce stereotypical behaviors, while teacher biases and school culture could further perpetuate gender norms. Taher (2021) and Gaddi et al. (2024) highlight that despite technological advancements, girls still face fewer opportunities than boys in accessing and benefiting from quality education. Empirical evidence from European countries similarly points to the underrepresentation of women in technical fields such as engineering, science, mathematics, and computing, while women are overrepresented in humanities, languages, education, and the arts. This disparity reinforces traditional gender roles and widens the gender inequality gap.

Regarding religion, no significant differences were found in the antecedents of gender stereotyping for Cognitive Factors ($p = 0.151$), Family Factors ($p = 0.452$), and Socio-cultural Factors ($p = 0.174$). This indicates that, regardless of their religious affiliation, students are similarly affected by these factors, reflecting shared cultural and social norms that transcend specific religious teachings. The uniformity may stem from the cultural context in which students, irrespective of religion, are exposed to similar societal expectations regarding gender roles. However, there was a significant difference in Individual Factors ($p = 0.010$), suggesting that religious affiliation influences students' perceptions of gender. Religious beliefs and teachings may shape attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors related to gender roles and expectations. Orbeta (2019) noted that while patriarchal relations are central to many global religions, this is not universally applicable. Some religious orders emphasize cooperation and respect for women, while others prioritize male leadership but indirectly allow women spaces to practice agency and exercise power.

In response to the findings, schools can adopt several practical strategies to address and reduce gender stereotyping within their communities, fostering a more inclusive environment for all students. Addressing perceptions based on physical appearance could be highly impactful. Schools could hold workshops or activities that encourage students to value one another for their character and abilities rather than

looks. This might involve sessions where students share their unique skills and talents or participate in discussions focused on recognizing internal qualities over external ones. Reflective activities where students confront their own biases around appearance could also promote a healthier, more respectful peer culture.

Another effective approach involves tackling career-related stereotypes that often guide students' ambitions. Schools can emphasize personalized career counseling that supports students' genuine interests and strengths, regardless of gender. Hosting speakers from diverse professions and highlighting non-traditional career paths within the curriculum could broaden students' perspectives, helping them see themselves in roles free from gender constraints.

Given the strong influence of family expectations on students' views of gender roles, schools could also foster family engagement. Organizing family-oriented events, such as an "Inclusion Day," would offer parents insights into the benefits of gender-neutral roles both at home and in the broader community. Schools could provide resources or workshops that encourage families to model gender-inclusive behavior, showing children that domestic and professional roles can be shared equitably.

On a broader level, integrating discussions about emotional well-being into school programs can help dismantle stereotypes around emotional expression. Activities such as group discussions, role-playing, and guest talks from mental health professionals could foster a more open attitude towards emotions, particularly for male students who may feel restricted by societal norms. Encouraging all students to express themselves freely can lead to healthier, more authentic relationships.

Lastly, schools might consider implementing community-wide initiatives aimed at breaking down stereotypes. For example, organizing a "Breaking Stereotypes Week" would allow students to share their insights, engage with peers, and become more aware of the diversity within their community. Student-led campaigns and collaborative projects that

champion gender inclusivity can have a lasting impact, helping cultivate a school culture where everyone feels valued and understood.

CONCLUSIONS

The study's findings provide a deeper understanding of the antecedents of gender stereotyping among senior high school students, highlighting the roles of individual, cognitive, familial, and socio-cultural factors, with family emerging as the most influential. This emphasizes the critical role families play in perpetuating gender stereotypes, particularly through expectations surrounding household responsibilities and gendered roles. The findings also reveal differences in gender perceptions across academic strands and the impact of religion on individual perspectives, underscoring the need for targeted interventions to address these specific influences and promote a more inclusive approach to gender in educational settings.

The study recommends actionable steps to address these findings. For students, fostering awareness and self-reflection about the factors shaping their gender perceptions can empower them to identify and counteract stereotypes. For teachers and school staff, incorporating gender-sensitive materials, inclusive language, and diverse instructional strategies can help create a classroom environment that challenges gender biases. School administrators are encouraged to implement targeted policies and programs to address the root causes of gender stereotypes and foster a supportive and inclusive school climate. Families are also integral to this effort; parents and guardians can engage in open discussions about gender roles, model equitable behavior, and encourage children to explore diverse interests and activities without gendered constraints.

For future research, this study provides a foundation for examining the influence of different academic strands on students' views of gender and exploring more focused intervention strategies to address gender stereotyping in educational and family contexts.

Limitations and Future Directions

This study faced several limitations that warrant consideration. First, challenges in data collection, including potential response biases and the limited geographic scope, may impact the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, the study captures students' gender perceptions at a single point in time, restricting insights into how these perceptions might evolve over time. To address these limitations, future research could incorporate longitudinal designs to track changes in gender perceptions and stereotypes over time. Qualitative methods, such as in-depth interviews or focus groups, are also recommended to delve into individual experiences and provide deeper insights into the complex factors influencing gender stereotypes.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The researchers extend their heartfelt gratitude to all individuals who contributed to the successful completion of this study. They acknowledge the invaluable guidance and unwavering support of their mentors, whose expertise greatly enriched this research. The researchers also express their sincere appreciation to the participants for their participation and openness, as their insights were vital to the study's outcomes. Gratitude is further extended to colleagues, friends, and family members for their constant encouragement throughout the research process. Lastly, the researchers are deeply thankful for the resources and opportunities provided by their institution, which played an integral role in the accomplishment of this work.

REFERENCES

- Bian, L., Leslie, S., & Cimpian, A. (2017). Gender stereotypes about intellectual ability emerge early and influence children's interests. *Science*, 355(6323), 389–391. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aah6524>
- Bosak, J., Eagly, A., Diekmann, A., & Sczesny, S. (2017). Women and men of the past, present, and future: Evidence of dynamic gender stereotypes in Ghana. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, 49(1), 115–129. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022022117738750>
- Cabrigas, M. E. J. C., Biyoyo, L. E. B., Calumpag, E. P. L., Gaddi, J. A. G., Gales, M., Mapa, C. F. G., ... & Valledor, J. F. (2024). Impluwensiya ng balbal sa makrong kasanayan ng mga mag-aaral sa ikalabing-isang baitang. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(5), 589–606. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11145925>
- Dacoylo, E. J. A., Arcaya, K. M. Q., Patubo, J. J. H. M., Pesidas, V. A. A., & Gaddi, J. A. G. (2024). Relevance of time management skills to students' classroom performance. *International Journal of Research*, 11(5), 242–254. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11369959>
- Department of Education (DepEd). (2019). DepEd strengthens STEM education in public schools. Department of Education Press Release. Retrieved from <https://www.deped.gov.ph>
- Diaz, S. E., Pontillo, K. M. A., Nebria, G. G., Serato, J. C., Gaddi, J. A. G., Ariar, M. D., & Orillaneda, E. M. R. (2024). Awareness and appreciation of local cultural heritage of Surigao City. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 07(05). <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/v7-i5-53>
- Dökmen, Z. (2012). *Toplumsal cinsiyet sosyal psikolojik açıklamalar*. Istanbul: Remzi Kitapevi.
- Ebert, W. M., Jost, L., & Jansen, P. (2024). Gender stereotypes in preschoolers' mental rotation. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 15, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1284314>
- Eliot, L. B. E., Galigao, J. D., Ortiz, T. V., Gaddi, J. A. G., Pongcol, A. M. P., & Entendez, C. E. (2024). Influence of colors on the memorization skill of senior high school students. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 07(06), 3702–3709. <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/v7-i6-17>

- Ellemers, N. (2018). Morality and social identity. In M. van Zomeren & J. F. Dovidio (Eds.), *The Oxford handbook of the human essence* (pp. 147–158). Oxford University Press.
- Ertl, B., Luttenberger, S., & Paechter, M. (2017). The impact of gender stereotypes on the self-concept of female students in STEM subjects with an under-representation of females. *Frontiers in Psychology, 8*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.00703>
- Fawcett Society. (2023, October 26). Gender stereotypes significantly limiting children's potential, causing lifelong harm, commission finds. *Fawcett Society*. <https://www.fawcettsociety.org.uk/news/gender-stereotypes-significantly-limiting-childrens-potential-causing-lifelong-harm-commission-finds>
- Ford, K., Bellis, M. A., Hughes, K., Judd, N., & Barton, E. R. (2024). Exploring the intergenerational continuity of ACEs amongst a sample of Welsh male prisoners: A retrospective cross-sectional study. *Child Protection and Practice, 3*, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chipro.2024.100053>
- Gaddi, J. A. (2024). Tracer study of senior high school graduates from a private school in the Philippines. *Journal of Education, Learning, and Management, 1*(2), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13924128>
- Gaddi, J. A. G. (2024). Graduate tracer study of the senior high school of St. Paul University Surigao, Philippines 2021–2022. *Global Journal of Applied Sciences and Technology, 6*(3), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13382610>
- Gaddi, J. A. G., Serato, J. C., Digal, E. S., & Frias, J. L. (2024). Learning gap assessment in Filipino sa Piling Larangan (Tech-Voc). *European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements, 5*(3), 51–55. <https://scholarzest.com/index.php/ejhea/article/view/4411>
- Gaddi, J. A., Entendez, C., Angob, W. M., Orillaneda, E. M., Elicano, M. L., Behagan, J. K. M., Ajoc, S., Peña, A. K., & Galvez, B. R. M. (2024). Courseware development in education: A literature review. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 7*(1), 842–847. <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V7-i1-83>
- Gaddi, J. A. G. (2024). Learning gap in Filipino sa Piling Larangan (Teknikal-Bokasyunal): An assessment. *International Research Journal of Science, Technology, Education, and Management, 4*(2), 88–95. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12730335>

- Gaddi, J. A., Osorio, I. M., Geotina, A., Plaza, S., Orillaneda, E. M., Alentajan, J., & Maarat, J. (2024). Factors influencing entrepreneurial intention of the senior high school students. *International Journal of Science and Management Studies (IJSMS)*, 7(1), 10–24. <https://doi.org/10.51386/25815946/ijms-v7i1p102>
- Gul Unlu, D. (2021). Determining gender stereotypes based on physical appearance expectations in interpersonal communication processes: An intercultural comparison between Turkey and Portugal. *Online Journal of Communication and Media Technologies*, 11(1), e202102. <https://doi.org/10.30935/ojcm/9576>
- Islam, K. M. M., & Asadullah, M. N. (2018). Gender stereotypes and education: A comparative content analysis of Malaysian, Indonesian, Pakistani, and Bangladeshi school textbooks. *PLoS ONE*, 13(1), 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0190807>
- Languing, B. J., Ferol, J. M. G., Gaddi, J. A., Sarayan, I. R., Bulay, B. Z., & Sarvida, J. H. G. (2023). Factors affecting Grade 11 students' study habits during the pandemic. *Cognizance Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 3(12), 274–288. <https://doi.org/10.47760/cognizance.2023.v03i12.022>
- Law, F., McGuire, L., Winterbottom, M., & Rutland, A. (2021). Children's gender stereotypes in STEM following a one-shot growth mindset intervention in a science museum. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, Article 641695. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.641695>
- Lewicki, P. (1986). Processing information about covariations that cannot be articulated. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Learning, Memory, and Cognition*, 12(1), 135–146. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0278-7393.12.1.135>
- Lumen Learning. (2023). Reading: Gender and socialization. In *Introductory sociology*. <https://courses.lumenlearning.com/suny-herkimer-intro-to-sociology-1/chapter/reading-gender/>
- McCombes, S. (2019). Descriptive research: Definition, types, methods & example. Retrieved from <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/descriptive-research/>
- Orbeta, A. (2019). Education trends and gender parity in the Philippines. *Philippine Institute for Development Studies*. <https://www.pids.gov.ph>
- Pew Research Center. (2019). Religious composition by country, 2019. Retrieved from <https://www.pewresearch.org>

- Platil, J. R. C., Sapalaran, J. M. C., Ortiz, S. M. A., Guiritan, Z. A. G., Ceniza, T. M. D., Cuizon, H. W. L., & Gaddi, J. A. G. (2024). Bisa ng pagtuturo sa makasaysayang pagpapahalaga sa kontemporaryong kulturang Pilipino ng mga mag-aaral sa Humanidades at Agham Panlipunan. *International Journal of Research*, 11(6), 82–94. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11561618>
- Rost, D. H., Sparfeldt, J. R., Dickhäuser, O., & Schilling, S. R. (2005). Dimensional comparisons in subject-specific academic self-concepts and achievements: A quasi-experimental approach. *Learning and Instruction*, 15(6), 557–570. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2005.08.003>
- Shafi, S. (2021). The representations and implications of gender stereotypes portrayed in three selected TV advertisements shown in Bangladesh: A critical interpretation. *Journal of Humanities and Applied Social Sciences*, 3(4), 299–314. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jhass-10-2020-0185>
- Tabassum, N., & Nayak, B. S. (2021). Gender stereotypes and their impact on women’s career progressions from a managerial perspective. *IIM Kozhikode Society & Management Review*, 10(2), 192–208. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2277975220975513>
- Taher, S. S. (2021). The influence of gender stereotyping and demographic factors on academic choice: The case of the University of Debrecen. *The Hungarian Educational Research Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1556/063.2021.00056>
- UNESCO. (n.d.). Gender stereotypes. Retrieved from <https://www.unesco.org/en/tags/gender-stereotypes>
- Women and Gender Institute. (2022). Workplace discrimination. *Manila Christian College*. Retrieved from <https://www.mc.edu.ph/wagi/resources>
- World Economic Forum. (2021). *Global gender gap report 2021*. Retrieved from https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_GGGR_2021.pdf
- World Economic Forum. (2023). *Global gender gap report 2023*. Retrieved from https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_GGGR_2023.pdf
- Zawisza, M., Luyt, R., Zawadzka, A. M., & Buczny, J. (2018). Cross-cultural sexism and the effectiveness of gender (non)traditional advertising: A comparison of purchase intentions in Poland, South Africa, and the United Kingdom. *Sex Roles: A Journal of Research*, 79(11–12), 738–751. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-018-0906-8>